

Technical Notes on the construction of the COVINFORM Risk Index

This report provides an overview of the *technical* work undertaken in the development of the risk assessment model and risk index displayed on the COVINFORM dashboard. In this report, we describe the process followed to download, clean, and reformat data before ingestion into our risk model as well as provide technical details of this modelling and how we compute countries' risk scores. The conceptual and theoretical background of the COVINFORM risk assessment methodology is provided in the project's deliverables ('[D2.3 Section 3](#)' and '[D2.7 Section 6](#)').

1. Data Processing

Data for the COVINFORM risk model was collected from various sources. The list of included indicators, their reporting formats and definitions, links to the original sources and directions of scale can be found in the [COVINFORM Risk Assessment Indicator Details](#) document. The distribution of indicators across domains and subdomains can be found in the [COVINFORM Risk Model Framework](#).

Data downloaded from its original source was processed into individual standard data frames¹ with information including:

- **Indicator description** – Text describing the indicator in the manner described by the source.
- **Country name** – The names of the 27 EU member states and UK were standardised across all datasets and where the two or three letter ISO 3166-1 country codes² were provided, these were converted into their full names.
- **Unit** – The units for which the data were measured (e.g., %GDP, per 1,000 inhabitants etc.).
- **Year/date** - Where available, annual values were used. If the dataset reported daily data (typical when reporting epidemiological data pertaining to COVID-19), the dates were specified in the year-month-day format.
- **Value** - Some datasets included other information such as age, sex, ethnicity, income band etc.

After initial cleaning and formatting, the following steps were taken so that a single value for each country, each indicator and each year could be obtained to feed into the COVINFORM risk model:

1. Where multiple disaggregations and/or units were available in a dataset, the most appropriate disaggregation and unit was chosen. For example, if data (such as unemployment rate) was available for different subgroups of the population (such as male, female and total population), the values for total population was selected.
2. Where data was recorded on a daily or weekly basis, it was either averaged to produce a single representative value for the year (e.g. hospital occupancy rates, changes in mobility) or the last recorded value for the year was taken (% of population fully vaccinated by the end of the year)
3. Where epidemiological data (such as covid-19 cases, tests and deaths) was available daily or weekly, the cumulative value on the last available day of the year was taken.

¹ A data frame is a data structure that organizes data into a 2-dimensional table of rows and columns.

² Available at <https://www.iso.org/obp/ui/#search>

4. In cases where the original data are provided as absolute measures of the indicator, we obtain a relative measure by dividing the data by either population size (per 1,000 inhabitants) or, in the case of financial data by GDP (% GDP).
5. If data was in different monetary units, it was converted to a standard unit (ideally Purchasing Power Parity (PPP)) by using the average exchange rate for the year.
6. Where data was missing for some countries, attempts were made to fill in the gaps with values taken from other available sources providing the same or a comparable indicator.
 - a. Note: To ensure data quality and to maintain data comparability across sources, the trends and values of the same indicator obtained from the main and alternative source were visually inspected. This process also included evaluating the indicator definitions by each data source and checking whether it matched the primary source definition.

A CSV file for each year and subdomain of the model is then saved to the data lake for further retrieval and processing. These further preprocessing stages are documented in [Section 2.2](#), as they include decisions made and justified in the specific context of the COVINFORM risk model.

2. Building the Risk Index

The COVINFORM Risk Index (also referred to as the COVINFORM Risk Model) is a composite indicator (i.e., a mathematical combination of indicators into a single value intended to summarise or measure a complex multi-dimensional phenomenon), obtained by *hierarchical* aggregation. This means that single indicators belonging to each subdomain are combined into a first composite indicator (*subdomain score*), the subdomain scores are then combined into a second composite of composite indicators (*domain scores*) and finally the domain scores are combined into the final *risk score* (the final composite indicator).

Figure 1. Hierarchical representation of the risk framework.

For example, given the hierarchic structure of our risk framework (Figure 1), the subdomain score for the subdomain *Social-Consequences* is obtained by combining the indicators *food insecurity* and *crime*; in a similar way subdomain scores for the *health*, *economic* and *environmental* consequences are obtained; all these subdomain scores are combined into the *Consequences* domain score. The procedure is repeated for the other domains and the domain scores are combined into the final composite indicator (the COVINFORM Risk Index).

More precisely, the COVINFORM Risk Index is a *weighted* composite indicator. In practice, this means that when building the composite, we place on indicators and scores a weight, i.e., a value reflecting the importance of the concept underlying the indicator/score in the composite. Two mathematical formulations commonly used to obtain weighted composite indicators are the *geometric* and *arithmetic* aggregation. We provide two alternatives of the COVINFORM Risk Index, each using arithmetic or geometric aggregation. The formulae for computing the (weighted) final risk score are as follows:

$$r_A = 0.25 * d_V + 0.25 * d_C + 0.25 * d_R + 0.25 * d_T$$

$$r_G = (d_V + 1)^{0.25} * (d_C + 1)^{0.25} * (d_R + 1)^{0.25} * (d_T + 1)^{0.25}$$

Equation 1: The COVINFORM Risk Index formula (arithmetically and geometrically aggregated versions)

r_A and r_G represent the arithmetically and geometrically aggregated scores respectively, whilst equal weights are used for each of the four domains (vulnerability d_V , consequences d_C , resilience d_R , and threat d_T). Further information on these formulae (included generalised versions for other hierarchical levels within the risk model) is available in Section [2.6. Aggregation](#).

The details on the derivation of the overall COVINFORM Risk Index, domain, and subdomains scores are provided in [D2.7](#), submitted in August 2023. The scores are computed separately for each country and for each time period in our framework, therefore a risk score for baseline, first-phase, and post-vaccine periods (2019, 2020, and 2021) will be obtained, allowing for drawing insights on the change of the risk score over time.

Following the data preprocessing steps, imputation, transformation, and normalisation of the indicator data is necessary before computing the subdomain scores.

2.1. Correlation between Indicators

Computing a correlation (Pearson) matrix of continuous indicators allows us to consider the relations between the information they provide. If two indicators are highly correlated (having a Pearson correlation coefficient greater than 0.85⁸), they are providing similar information to the composite index. For example, both income distribution and poverty rate data may provide information on financial hardship across a population – if highly correlated, a model that uncritically aggregates this data may place more emphasis on financial hardship as a risk factor than intended. As one input should

not be weighted unequally against another, the default approach is to adjust the weighting of these indicators in aggregation – the process used to do so is detailed in [Weighting \(Section 2.5\)](#).

2.2. Indicator Preprocessing

Several transformations need to be performed on indicators before they can be used to compute risk scores. Zero values and strings marking not available data are standardised; where necessary, scales are inverted: for each indicator we want a consistent direction i.e., “the lower the value the better”, which is achieved by simply multiplying data values by -1 for indicators where higher values are “better”. Deciding which direction is “better” for each indicator is not always obvious and largely context (subdomain) dependent. For example, a high number of aircraft passengers might be a positive if we are looking to evaluate the development of a country’s transport industry (higher values are better), but a negative if we are looking to evaluate the exposure of a country to viral spread (lower values are better).

Lastly, some indicators will possess outliers: identifying these outliers is non-trivial, and we have adopted the approach recommended by the European Commission’s Joint Research Centre⁹ and implemented in the Transitions Performance Index 2021¹⁰. This involves computing a dataset’s *skewness* and *kurtosis*, measures of the asymmetry and “tailedness” of the dataset’s distribution, respectively. A dataset (in the case of the risk index, an indicator) can be considered to possess outliers if it has an absolute skewedness of greater than 2 and a kurtosis of greater than 3.5. It is important to handle these outliers before normalisation: as normalisation processes like rescaling seek to convert indicators to a standard range, the normalised indicator can be distorted if the minima and maxima are outliers.

For the COVINFORM Risk Index, each indicator meeting the criteria outlined above will be *log-transformed* (i.e., the indicators values are replaced by their logarithm) before normalisation. Due to the presence of negative values (which cannot be log-transformed), we must first make all values positive whilst preserving the range, for which the following formula was used:

$$x' = \log \log (x - (x) + a) , \text{ where } a = 0.01((x) - (x))$$

Equation 2: Log transformation function adjusted to handle negative values.

2.3. Imputation

Following preprocessing there are still some indicators with missing values that cannot be imputed in bulk using ‘Last Observation Carried Forward’ (LOCF) or similar techniques based on data from previous years. The most suitable imputation technique for each indicator depends primarily on whether the data is ‘missing completely at random’ (MCAR), ‘missing at random’ (MAR), or ‘missing not at random’ (MNAR), as well as the correlation between indicators in a subdomain. These factors will determine the most appropriate imputation method missing for a given indicator.

The most frequently used imputation method in the COVINFORM risk index is the Multiple Imputation by Chained Equations (MICE) approach, used for those indicators where data were historically unavailable in a given country, or where the reasons for this lack of data collection were deemed

independent of the other indicators in the subdomain, rendering the data either MCAR or MAR. A MICE approach is also dependent on other indicators in the given subdomain providing sufficient information to impute a similar value: for example, the number of doctors, hospital beds, and healthcare spending could reasonably be used to derive a statistical estimate of the number of nurses employed in a given year.

Other variables are not possible to impute, due to a lack of data for multiple years and little correlation between other present indicators. For example, international trade and adult population data could not reasonably be used to impute temperature data. In this case, temperature data would simply be ignored for this country/year combination when calculating a risk score, and the weights for other indicators adjusted accordingly.

2.4. Normalisation

Re-scaling, otherwise known as min-max normalisation, is used on all indicators across all subdomains. This method reduces the range of all indicators to (0, 1). Another common normalisation method, standardisation, was also considered. Standardisation makes indicators on different scale more easily comparable by transforming the data so that they have the same mean and the same measure of spread standard deviation.

Re-scaling was selected as it is less likely to reward exceptional behaviour in one indicator than standardisation, preferring an “average” score in many indicators to exceptional scores in a few. This is in-line with the goals expressed in the production of the COVINFORM risk model: namely, the desired focus on complex systems analysis that requires a data analysis that respects the importance of emergent and intersecting risk over and above risk in isolated domains. Other normalisation techniques considered include rankings (inappropriate due to ignoring degrees of difference between countries, which would be especially stark considering the small datasets in use) and categorical scores (which would require a broad range of expert input).

2.5. Weighting

Weights dictate the level of “influence” an indicator will have in each subdomain, and hence should represent the value we place upon each indicator, both in terms of importance and how one indicator may compensate for an information deficit in another. This is a challenging process, and several methods can be used in selecting indicator weights when building a composite index, each with their advantages and disadvantages. In constructing the COVINFORM Risk Index two key factors determining our choice were:

- Feasibility of expert judgement: due to the time and budget constraints of the project, the ability to access a suitable pool of domain experts across all required domains, and to conduct a form of multi-criteria decision analysis or a Delphi consensus approach was disregarded.
- Statistical considerations: the size of our sample is 28 (the number of countries for which we have data), a sample size deemed too small for computing statistically derived weights (e.g., using principal component analysis or factor analysis) with sufficient statistical significance.

Most composite indexes rely on equal weighting, implying that all indicators have the same “worth”. This is also the approach we have adopted for the COVINFORM Risk Index. The only exception to this is where two indicators in each subdomain are highly correlated (as defined in [Correlation between](#)

[Indicators \(Section 2.1.\)](#): in this case they are treated as a single indicator for the purposes of dividing weights between indicators, with this weight then divided between them. For example, if a given subdomain has five indicators, two of which are highly correlated, the weights of the respective indicators may be given as: [0.25, 0.25, 0.25, 0.125, 0.125].

2.6. Aggregation

For reasons outlined in [Weighting \(Section 2.5.\)](#) the choice of aggregation method should not rely on expert judgement. As subdomains have different numbers of indicators aggregation will inevitably provide some indicators with more “importance” than others when computing domain-level risk scores and final risk scores. The level of skew of this sort must be carefully accounted for, including setting limits of what level we are willing to accept, and putting into practice mitigation strategies where possible.

In the case of the COVINFORM Risk Index linear aggregation (e.g., arithmetic, the sum of weighted indicators) can be meaningfully applied, providing that all indicators are scaled consistently via normalisation (so that they can be meaningfully compared). Linear aggregations reward indicators proportionally to their weight and are easy to interpret but they imply full compensability (meaning that poor performance of some indicators might be compensated for by sufficiently high values in other indicators). This is not always desirable and non-compensatory methods would indeed be adequate in our case. However, they are time-consuming to implement due to reliance on expert judgments and have therefore been excluded. A non-linear approach like geometric aggregation (i.e., the product of weighted indicators) would, in our case, be a valid option to allow some degree of non-compensability while ensuring simplicity of computation (since expert judgement is not required). Geometric aggregation also has the benefit of rewarding improvement (higher scores) in indicators with lower means, more than it does identical improvement/score increase in indicators with higher means, which is useful in the context of lowering risk. For this reason, whilst both arithmetically and geometrically aggregated scores are available for download from the COVINFORM dashboard, geometrically aggregated scores are those displayed on the dashboard choropleth map.

Single path aggregation is preferred when computing the risk model. For example, only subdomain-level risk scores calculated using arithmetic aggregation are used when calculating domain-level risk scores using arithmetic aggregation, and likewise for geometric aggregation.

The formulae for the arithmetically and geometrically aggregated scores respectively are as follows:

$$r_A = \text{sum}(r'_A \odot w)$$

$$r_G = \text{prod}((r'_G + 1)^w)$$

Equation 3: General weighted arithmetic and geometric means functions

Arithmetically aggregated scores (r_A) for each country are computed as the sum of $r'_A \odot w$ where r'_A is the series of arithmetically aggregated scores from each domain and w provides the associated weights for each domain. \odot defines a simple element-wise multiplication of these components: for example, $[1,2] \odot [2,3]=[2,6]$. The sum of this resulting list is then the overall arithmetic score for that country. For geometrically aggregated scores (r_G), terms are defined

similarly to above, with the subscript G denoting the use of geometrically aggregated domain scores. The use of min-max normalisation to provide indicators with a common scale and aligned distribution (outlined in [2.4. Normalisation](#)) requires the addition of 1 to each score: this preserves the range of the data but ensures each value is greater than 1, ensuring that weights are applied appropriately. The resulting list is then multiplied element-by-element to produce the resulting score. This approach is applied across the index hierarchy, with domain scores computed from subdomains and subdomains from indicator data.

2.7. Ranking

Risk scores at the domain and overall levels are ranked to provide a basic and accessible comparison of risk between countries. While the overall ranking provides an average assessment of a country’s risk, rankings at domain level can provide interesting insights on countries profiles across the different dimensions of risk. Ranking is not performed at the subdomain level as subdomains do not contain sufficient information value to be able to have a meaningful ranking – without the additional context available at the domain level and above, such outputs may be misleading. Rankings are produced using both arithmetic and geometric aggregation, and these ranks are then further used to divide the index countries into quintiles¹² (five sets).

These rankings and quintile assignments are less information-dense than the risk scores themselves due to the removal of detail such as how close one country’s risk may be to another’s but are nevertheless useful in producing diagrammatic, visual, and interactive outputs (as in the form of the COVINFORM Dashboard) and being easy to understand and communicate. For this reason, the quintile assignments for each country may be considered the ‘final output’ of the COVINFORM risk model, by providing a categorical “high-low” style label to each country, and in each domain.

Figure 2. Colour-coded risk assessment choropleth within the Risk Assessment tab in the dashboard.